

Original Research Article

Assessment of Community-based Antenatal Care Services Provided by Midwives in River Nile State, Sudan, 2017

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Abstract

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This study aimed to assess the community-based antenatal care services provided by midwives in River Nile State, 2017. A cross-sectional community based study using structured questionnaire for collecting quantitative data, was conducted in River Nile State, 2017. Multi-stage cluster sampling technique was used. Three localities of the state were determined. The calculated sample size for women at reproductive age was divided between the selected localities proportional to size of midwives per each locality. Then simple random sample was used for the selection of midwives in each locality and 3 women were selected per midwife. A total of 92 midwives and 276 mothers were interviewed in this study. Generally mothers were satisfied with antenatal midwifery services. Mother's satisfaction was significantly related to the number of antenatal care visits and place of antenatal care examination. The majority of mothers sought antenatal care from medical doctors and the majority of mothers who sought antenatal care from midwives are satisfied with their service.

Keywords: Antenatal care, Family planning, Midwifery, Mothers satisfaction, River Nile, Services, Referral

INTRODUCTION

Worldwide approximately 303,000 women die while pregnant or giving birth in 2015, almost 830 deaths/day (Abd Elmoneim et al., 2014). An estimated 8 million more suffer serious illnesses and lifelong disabilities as a result of complications at the time of childbirth (Adegoke et al., 2011). Every year up to 2 million newborns die within the first 24 hours of life (Carr et al., 2011). There are 2.6 million stillbirths, 98% in low- and middle-income countries (Choulagai et al., 2013), of which approximately 45% occur during labor and birth (Dowswell et al., 2010). Millions more newborns suffer birth traumas that impair their development and future productivity. The overwhelming majority of these deaths occur in low-income countries and most of them could have been prevented. They happen because women, usually the poor and marginalized, have no access to functioning

health facilities or to qualified health personnel. In 2012, 40 million births in developing regions were not attended by skilled health personnel (FMOH, Multiple Indicators Cluster Survey, 2014). To cut this tragedy there is a need for two key components: a skilled birth attendant (SBA) and an enabling environment that includes drugs and equipment, a functional referral system and enabling policies (FMOH. Sudan Household Health Survey, 2010; Goals MD, Secretary-general UN, 2010). These health professionals should be motivated and located in the right place at the right time. SBA is defined as "an accredited health professional such as a midwife, doctor or nurse who has been educated and trained to manage normal (uncomplicated) pregnancies, childbirth and the immediate postnatal period, and in the identification, management and referral of complications in women and

newborns” (Graham et al., 2001). Studies have demonstrated a positive correlation between the proportion of deliveries taking place with an SBA and a reduction in maternal deaths (Hatem et al., 2008; International Confederation of Midwives, 2016). Increasing women’s access to high-quality midwifery services has become a focus of global efforts to realize the right of every woman to the best possible health care during pregnancy and childbirth. In Sudan such skills at community level were designed to be carried out by midwives. According to World Health Organization (WHO) and International Confederation of Midwives (ICM), trained midwives are expected to provide care of women during pregnancy, labour, and the postpartum period, as well as care of the newborn, registration of newborn births and deaths, and maternal mortality. Measures aimed at preventing health problems in pregnancy, the detection of abnormal conditions, the procurement of medical assistance when necessary, and the execution of emergency measures in the absence of medical help are also expected from the trained midwives (International Confederation of Midwives, Essential competencies for basic midwifery practice, 2016; International Labor Office, 2012).

Problem Statement

Three quarters of all maternal deaths in Sudan occurred during delivery and the immediate postpartum period (Koblinsky et al., 2006). As a response a comprehensive programme to reduce maternal mortality was established. Midwives are the cornerstone of this programme. Basic and in-service training is going on and efforts to equip midwives with necessary material is accelerated in the last years. Although maternal mortality was profoundly decreased by the end of 2015, Still Sudan failed to meet the MDGs target (Koblinsky et al., 2006). River Nile state has many rural areas in which the tendency is for home delivery which performed by midwives. The coverage with midwives in the state is 72%, and home delivery in the state exceeds 70%. With this coverage and with high percentage of home delivery, it seems that the role of midwives in reducing maternal mortality and ensure safe delivery and neonatal health could be of benefit provided that they were equipped to do that, they were committed and their role is appreciated by the community, and the community is satisfied with their services.

Justification

Midwives workforce represents the backbone of community-based reproductive health services and form important path for lowering maternal mortality in a country like Sudan, where most deliveries (72%) still take place at home (Lawn et al., 2011). Since midwife’s act as the first

line of defense, their services need to be scientifically assessed in River Nile State in order to provide information on the actual level of acquired knowledge and skills and to determine accordingly the future training they need. Also, when the services are studied and analyzed, the quality can be improved.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Giving birth can be a potentially life-threatening process for mother and baby in developing countries. It was demonstrated that many of the causes of maternal deaths are substantially preventable and treatable with low-cost interventions. Skilled birth attendants (including midwives) is one of these interventions.

Definition and scope of practice

Midwifery encompasses care of women during pregnancy, labor, and the postpartum period, as well as care of the newborn. It includes measures aimed at preventing health problems in pregnancy, the detection of abnormal conditions, the procurement of medical assistance when necessary, and the execution of emergency measures in the absence of medical help (International Labor Office, 2012). It is a health science as well as a health profession which implement the above measures, besides sexual and reproductive health of women throughout their lives. A professional in midwifery is known as a midwife. The International Labour Organization (ILO) describes midwives as the primary professional group to provide midwifery (Lincetto et al., 2006). The ICM defines the work of midwives and core competencies and standards for their education and practice (Minimum package of antenatal care services defined, 2017).

According to ICM a midwife is a person who has successfully completed a midwifery education programme that is duly recognized in the country where it is located and that is based on the ICM Essential Competencies for Basic Midwifery Practice and the framework of the ICM Global Standards for Midwifery Education; who has acquired the requisite qualifications to be registered and/or legally licensed to practice midwifery and use the title ‘midwife’; and who demonstrates competency in the practice of midwifery (International Confederation of Midwives, Essential competencies for basic midwifery practice, 2016).

The midwife is recognized as a responsible and accountable professional who works in partnership with women to give the necessary support, care and advice during pregnancy, labor and the postpartum period, to conduct births on the midwife’s own responsibility and to provide care for the newborn and the infant. The midwife has an important task in health counselling and

education, not only for the woman, but also within the family and the community. This work should involve antenatal education, preparation for parenthood and child care. A midwife may practice in any setting including the home, community, hospitals, clinics or health units (Minimum package of antenatal care services defined, 2017).

Roles and Responsibilities of Midwives

Midwives as part of the community and as part of the health system play an important role. The role may differ from community to another and may differ between countries. Still it is considered as an essential role. Midwives are care-givers, coordinators, leaders, communicators, managers, educators, counselors, family planner, advisors, records keeper and supervisors (Report S. Stillbirths, 2016). Details of the various roles and responsibilities of midwives are given below:

- Care-givers: as they provide high quality antenatal and postnatal care to maximize the women's health during and after pregnancy, detect problems early and manage or refer for any complications.
- Coordinators: as they coordinate care for all women. Coordinator ensures holistic, voluntary and social services for pregnant women when appropriate so that every women's birth experience regardless of risk factor.
- Leaders: their role is to plan, provide and review a women's care, with her input and agreement, from the initial antenatal assessment through to the postnatal period. Midwife's leading role reduces admission to hospital and results in significantly less intervention during birth.
- Communicators: as they understand the effectiveness of communication. It helps to develop trust relationship with pregnant women and family members. The midwife has to communicate effectively with pregnant women and family members as well as others so that they can share their all problems.
- Managers: which is a great role for them. Midwives manage all the circumstances where appropriate and can recognize and refer women to obstetricians and other specialists in a timely when necessary.
- Educators: as they provide high quality, culturally sensitive health education in order to promote healthy, helpful family life and positive parenting.
- Counselors: as they provide information and counsel pregnant women on prenatal self-care including nutrition, hygiene, breastfeeding and danger signs in pregnancy and childbirth.
- Family planners: as they also counsel people regarding family planning. They provide all information about all kind of family planning methods and help couple to take decision.
- Advisers: as they give advice on development of birth plan and promote the concept of birth preparedness.

They also give advice during complicated situation so that it will help them to take decision.

- Record keepers: which is an integral part of midwifery practice. It helps making continuity of care easier and enabling identify problem in early stage.
- Supervisors: as they supervising and assisting mothers during antenatal period, monitoring the condition of the fetus and using their knowledge to identify early sings complication.

Midwives are important providers of care for childbearing women all over the world, especially rural areas where women are rely on midwives so much and seek their help and consultation. Main areas which midwives known with are:

Antenatal Care

Antenatal care (ANC) is a healthcare during pregnancy. It is one of the "four pillars" of safe motherhood, as formulated by the Maternal Health and Safe Motherhood Programme, division of Family Health, of the World Health Organization (WHO). The other three pillars are family planning, clean/safe delivery and essential obstetric care. This package was created to ensure that women should be able to go safely through pregnancy, childbirth and have healthy infants. This will ultimately prevent the terrible outcomes such as maternal death, perinatal and infant death (Robinson et al., 1983).

WHO recommends at least four antenatal care (ANC) visits for all pregnant women, ideally at 16, 24–28, 32, and 36 weeks (Scott and Ronsmans, 2009). In low-income countries, about 68% of mothers complete at least one ANC visit and almost 60% complete four or more visits (Stanton et al., 2007). In Nepal approximately half of the women completed four or more ANC visits (Suleiman Abd Gabbar, 2010). Almost half of the women worldwide, and especially in developing countries do not receive these recommended four visits. Reduced attendance of ANC is associated with many unwanted events such as delivery of low birth weight babies and more neonatal deaths. ANC include education on nutrition, potential problems with pregnancy or childbirth, child care and prevention or detection of disease during pregnancy (Robinson et al., 1983).

SUBJECTS AND METHODS

Study Design and Setting and Population

A cross-sectional community-based study using quantitative method.

The study was conducted in River Nile State which is located between Latitudes 16-22 north and Longitudes 32-35 south. The State's area is 124,000 square Kilometers. The population is 1,393,467. The women at

Table 1. Distribution of calculated sample size married women per selected localities

Locality	No. of midwives working at community level	%	Sample size women (3 per midwives)	Sample Size Midwives
Atbara	73	29.5	81	27
Elmatamma	87	35.0	96	32
Barbar	88	35.5	99	33
Total	248	100%	276	92

reproductive age are 338,526. It ranked as sixth state in terms of area among the Sudan states. It has 7 localities, 706 villages and city blocks. There is a midwifery school in Atbara with an estimated production of 100 midwives if functioning at its full capacity. The localities are: Addamer, Atbara, Barbar, Abuhamad, Shendi, Elmatamma, and Elbuheera. The study population divided for the purpose of study to; Midwives and Married women.

Inclusion criteria

For midwives, all midwives who worked at the community village and city blocks, Midwives who are living in the area and Midwives who are working for more than one year. For married women, the criteria included the Women who delivered within 3 months, and Women who delivered anywhere (home and hospital).

Exclusion criteria

For midwives, Midwives who worked at hospitals were excluded and for married women, Women who delivered more than months and who came to the study area after delivery.

Sample Size

For the married women the sample size was calculated using this formula: $n = z^2 pq / d^2$ Where: n = the sample size. z (the standard normal deviation) = 1.96 at 95% CI. p (mother satisfaction) = 0.90 (28). q = 0.10. d = 0.05. Design effect = 2.

$n = [z^2 pq / d^2] * 2$, so $n = (1.96)^2 * (0.90 * 0.10) / (0.05)^2$ and $n = 138 * 2 = 276$

For each 3 married women the researcher has interviewed one midwife, so the sample size of midwives was $(276/3) = 92$ midwives. (1:3 was obtained after personal communication with midwives).

Sampling Technique

Multi-stage cluster sampling technique was used for

selecting the localities which will be representative for the state. Three localities have been selected accordingly. These localities were Atbara, Elmatamma, and Barbar. The calculated sample size for married women then divided between the three selected localities proportional to size of midwives per each locality (total sample of married women * no. of midwives in the locality/total no. of midwives). Then simple random sample was used for the selection of midwives in each locality. While 3 women were selected with any midwife.(Table 1)

Data collection tools and technique (Questionnaire)

The data were collected by using structured pre-tested pre-coded questionnaire for collecting quantitative data from midwives. The questionnaire included 4 main sections. Section one covered the demographic information and midwife's qualification (graduation school, years of experience, training courses), section two concerned about antenatal care services provided by midwives, section three covered the delivery care services provided by the midwives, and lastly section four was for postnatal care services provided by midwives.

Second structured pre-tested pre-coded questionnaire for the mothers. It also included 4 main sections, section one covered the demographic information of the mothers, section two concerned about antenatal care services received by mothers, section three covered the delivery care services received by the mothers, and lastly section four was for postnatal care services received by mothers.

To facilitate well understanding to participants, both questionnaires were translated into Arabic language. Checklist used for assessing the midwife's kit contents status and completeness through direct observation.

Study variables

The dependent variable of study was Mothers' satisfaction with community-based midwifery services. Independent variables included; Antenatal care variables, Delivery care variables and postnatal care variables. Background variables were the Age, Residence, Education, Occupation and Number of children.

Table 2. Distribution of mothers according to general characteristics in River Nile State, Sudan, 2017 (n=276)

Variable	Categories	No.	Percentage
Age (years) (n=276)	Less than 25	93	33.7
	25 to 40	175	63.4
	More than 40	8	2.9
Locality (n=276)	Babar	99	35.5
	Elmatamma	96	35.1
	Atbara	81	29.3
Education (n=276)	Illiterate	17	6.2
	School education	111	36.4
	University and above	158	57.2
Mother job (n=276)	Housewife	255	92.4
	Employee	21	7.6
Number of children (n=276)	Less 3	110	39.9
	3 to 5	130	47.1
	More 5	36	13.0

Data management and Analysis

After completion of the field work, data was entered and cleaned using Standard Package of Social Services (SPSS) software version (Robinson et al., 1983). Data was analyzed using the same software. Frequency, tables and figures were formulated as appropriate to give clear description of the study population. Further analysis was conducted including regression analysis. The level of statistical significance considered at < 0.05 .

Ethical Consideration

Ethical clearance from the Sudan Medical Specialization Board (SMSB), and River Nile State Ministry of Health ethical committee was obtained. The midwives and women at reproductive age were informed about the objectives of the study and written consent was obtained from them. Rights of respondents and confidentiality was assured.

RESULTS

A total of 276 mothers were interviewed during this study in the River Nile State from three localities: Atbara (81), Elmatamma (96), and Barbar (99). The response rate was 100%. Results were displayed in tables and figures. About two thirds of the included mother were at 25- 40 years, 57.2% of them were graduated, and 92.4% of the mothers were housewives (Table 2).

Regarding ANC follow up approximately all mothers were on regular ANC follow up. Medical doctors were the antenatal care services provider for the majority of the mothers (93.1%) while midwives provided the services for only 10.6% of the mothers (Figures 1 and 2). Causes of not receiving their ANC services from nearby midwives

were seeking ultrasonography and other investigations in addition to supplementations or treatments given during pregnancy. Few mothers received their antenatal care from both doctors and midwives claiming that doctors are important for the above mentioned causes but midwives are much closer and they can tell the midwife about any abnormality they felt without shying and the midwives are more explicit with them.

For those who received ANC from midwives about (41%) of the mothers conducted more than 5 visits for the midwives in their antenatal care follow up, (52%) conducted 2 to 3 visits, and the remainder conducted less than 3 visits. When examination done by midwives the concentration was on abdominal examination (96.6%), conjunctivae, tongue, and nail examination for anemia (86.2%). Measuring the blood pressure and hearing fetal heart sounds were done in (10.3%) and (6.9%) respectively. The advices given by midwives were concentrating on ferrous sulphate and folic acid supplementation (89.7%), antenatal care follow up (69%), and nutrition with pregnancy (65.5%). Regarding problems during pregnancy there was one mother with Diabetes Mellitus, who was referred to a private hospital (Tables 3 and 4, Figure 3).

Mothers' satisfaction with midwifery antenatal care was high (86.2%). Mothers who dissatisfied said that the dissatisfaction with midwifery ANC services was because midwives did not measure the blood pressure, did not request investigations and did not give medications (Table 5)

Regarding ANC follow up approximately all mothers were on regular ANC follow up. Medical doctors were the antenatal care services provider for most of the mothers (93.1%) while midwives provided the services for only 10.6% of the mothers (Figures 1 and 2).

Causes of not receiving their ANC services from nearby midwives were seeking ultrasonography and other investigations in addition to supplementations or

Figure 1. Distribution of mothers according to ANC follow up in River Nile State, Sudan, 2017 (n= 276)

Figure 2. Distribution of mothers according to ANC provider in River Nile State, Sudan, 2017 (n= 276)

Table 3. Distribution of mothers according to Antenatal care events and services in River Nile State, Sudan, 2017

Variable	Categories	No.	Percentage
Place of receiving ANC services (n=274)	At the midwife home	16	5.8
	At a health center	15	5.5
	At a governance hospital	92	33.6
	At a private hospital/clinic	160	58.4
Number of ANC visits conducted by the midwife (n=29)	Less than 3	2	6.9
	3 to 5	15	51.7
	More than 5	12	41.4
Examination was done (n=29)	Weight	0	0.0
	Temperature	0	0.0
	Anemia (conjunctiva, tongue, nails)	25	86.2
	BP	3	10.3
	Abdominal examination	28	96.6
	Heard FHS	2	6.9
	Breast examination	0	0.0
Investigation requested (n=29)	Urine	14	48.3
	Hb	15	51.7
	Blood grouping	9	31.0

- All mothers were examined with their privacy saved.

Table 4. Showed the distribution of study participants – mothers - according to antenatal care events and services (n=276)

Variable	Categories	No.	Percentage
Were you advised to take tetanus toxoid? (n=29)	Yes	28	96.6
	No	1	3.4
If yes, how many doses? (n=29)	Less than 2	14	48.3
	2 to 4	2	6.9
	All	13	44.8
Have you taken Folic acid? (n=29)	Yes	21	72.4
	No	8	27.6
Have you taken Ferrous Sulphate? (n=29)	Yes	26	89.7
	No	3	10.3
Was the midwife advice you regarding (n=29)	ANC	20	69.0
	Nutrition with pregnancy	19	65.5
	Personal hygiene	26	89.7
	Exclusive breast feeding	0	0.0
	Delivery	12	41.4
	Ferrous Sulphate + Folic acid	0	0.0
Was there any problem in your last pregnancy? (n=29)	Yes	1	3.4
	No	28	96.6
Did the midwife refer you? (n=29)	Yes	1	3.4
	No	28	96.6
Are you satisfying with the midwifery ANC service? (n=29)	Yes	25	86.2
	No	4	13.8

Figure 3. Distribution of mothers according to the presence of problems during the last pregnancy in River Nile State, Sudan, 2017 (n= 29)

Table 5. Results of bivariate and multivariate analysis (logistic regression) for the factors that may associate with the mother satisfaction with antenatal care services provided by midwives, in River Nile State, Sudan, 2017 (n=25)

Variables (factors)	Mother satisfaction (n=25/satisfied)		Bivariate Analysis				Multivariate Analysis			
	No.	%	OR	95%CI		Pvalue	OR	95%CI		Pvalue
				From	To			From	To	
Age										
Less than 25	12	48.0	1.21	0.17	8.19	0.843	2.89	0.060	139.0	0.591
25 to 40	12	48.0								
More than 40	1	4.0								
Locality										
Atbara	14	56.0	0.22	0.04	1.03	0.055	0.18	0.21	1.67	0.134
Elmatamma	8	32.0								
Babar	3	12.0								
Education										
Illiterate	2	8.0	0.47	0.14	1.62	0.234	0.34	0.07	1.58	0.170
School education	8	32.0								
Graduated	15	60.0								
Examined in covered place										
Yes	24	96.0	5.74	3.52	8.64	< 0.001	3.27	1.99	5.71	0.016*
No	1	4.0								
Number of ANC visits										
Less than 3	1	4.0	8.73	0.85	89.54	0.068	2.29	1.62	4.67	0.049
3 to 5	12	48.0								
More than 5	12	48.0								
Advise for taking folic acid tablets										
Yes	18	72.0	1.16	0.10	13.19	0.901	1.15	0.35	1.86	0.633
No	7	28.0								

treatments given during pregnancy. Few mothers received their antenatal care from both doctors and midwives claiming that doctors are important for the above-mentioned causes, but midwives are much closer, and they can tell the midwife about any abnormality they felt without shying and the midwives are more explicit with them. For those who received ANC from midwives about (41%) of the mothers conducted more than 5 visits for the midwives in their antenatal care follow up, (52%) conducted 2 to 3 visits, and the remainder conducted less than 3 visits. When examination done by midwives the concentration was on abdominal examination (96.6%), conjunctivae, tongue, and nail examination for anemia (86.2%). Measuring the blood pressure and hearing fetal heart sounds were done in (10.3%) and (6.9%) respectively. The advices given by midwives were concentrating on ferrous sulphate and folic acid supplementation (89.7%), antenatal care follow up (69%), and nutrition with pregnancy (65.5%). Regarding problems during pregnancy there was one mother with Diabetes Mellitus, who was referred to a private hospital (Tables 2 and 3, Figure 3).

DISCUSSION

This study was conducted to assess community-based midwifery services in River Nile State, 2017. It was

involving collection of quantitative data from midwives and mothers using structured pre-tested questionnaires. Majority of the midwives took in-service training courses, but it was not regular or frequent and there was a long time in between these courses. In the last training courses midwives gained knowledge mainly, in addition to reporting skills with ignorance to clinical skills. Importance of additional training was revealed in a Cochrane review (United Nations, Assessing progress in Africa toward the Millennium Development Goals, 2014) in which they observed significant reduction in maternal morbidity, neonatal mortality, stillbirths and perinatal mortality, in addition to increased referral and improved breastfeeding after additional training intervention. Almost all midwives in this study recognized high risk pregnancy and when to refer during pregnancy and labor. This result is not in consistent with that found in a study conducted in Omdurman Maternity Hospital (WHO, Geneva, 2004) aimed to evaluate midwives' knowledge on antenatal care. This difference could be referred to the fact that these midwives worked mainly at the hospital, so they deal with already referred cases. About two thirds of the midwives' age was less than 40 years in contrast to that found in Omdurman Maternity Hospital study in which two thirds of the midwives' age was more than 40 years, most of this study midwives were educated while Omdurman Maternity Hospital study midwives were all educated. This is could be due to the context in which they lived as

this study midwives live in a rural area while those live in urban area. On monitoring the pregnant the Omdurman hospital study midwives were very concerned about history and examination while this study midwives concerned mainly about examination, the Maternity hospital midwives measuring the blood pressure and weighting the pregnant which were not done by this study midwives, few midwives in this study advised mothers about issues which were important for her and her baby during pregnancy while in the Maternity Hospital study the midwives were well informed to advice mothers regarding these issues. It was found that about half of the mothers completed three to four visits for the midwives in their antenatal care follow up, considerable part of them conducted more than five visits, while few mothers conducted less than three visits. This is different from the finding of a study conducted in Nepal (World Health Organization WHO Midwifery, 2016) which found that half of the women completed at least four ANC visits or more while the other half conducted less than four visits. This may be due to distance from the health facility and difficult transportation, less women awareness or education, less sample size in this study, or cultural differences between this study mothers and Nepal mothers.

Mother's satisfaction is considered to be an outcome of the delivery of health care services as well as a measure of its quality. It is a subjective and dynamic perception of the extent to which the expected health care is received. It is not important whether the mother is right or not, the important here is how the mother feels. The literatures showed that clients had various expectations that influenced their perception of care. These expectations were based on their own past experiences, experiences of friends and relations, myths about procedures done and societal values.

In a Cochrane review (WHO, UNICEF, UNFPA and the World Bank, 2015) aimed to compare midwife-led continuity models of care with other models of care for childbearing women and their infants suggests that women who received midwife-led continuity models of care were more likely to be satisfied with their care. It was found that there is association between number of antenatal care visits and mothers satisfaction. This result is similar to the finding of a Cochrane review (WHO, World Bank, UNICEF, UNFPA, 2010) aimed to compare the effects of antenatal care programmes with reduced visits for low-risk women with standard care in low and high income countries where it was found that women in all settings were less satisfied with the reduced visits schedule and perceived the gap between visits as too long although reduced visits may be associated with lower costs.

About 10% of the village midwives who interviewed in this study graduated for the second time as community midwife seeking for permanent job and better situation as they said. Very small percentage of the midwives were

supervised by the health visitors in their villages or city blocks and the duration in between these supervisory visits was long. This result was consistent with findings in a study conducted in North Kurdufan state (29). Supportive supervision is very important for quality control of the midwives work as the majority of them are not formally engaged in any health institution. Midwives themselves need these supervisory visits for getting advice and to get missing or replace consumed kits. Supportive supervision need to be done effectively by reproductive health administrations in all states but this does not happen due to many factors such as shortage of financial and human resources, transportation difficulties to all villages in River Nile State, and insecurity in some states.

The midwives are expected to provide antenatal care, delivery care, postnatal care, newborn care, referral, neonatal birth registration, maternal death registration, neonatal death registration, and family planning. They have an important task in health counselling and education, not only for the woman, but also within the family and the community. So the package of services provided by the midwives in this study is less than the expected by the definition. This may be due to lack of interest due to poor motivation, or because the majority of mothers were seeking health care from more qualified personnel and at health facilities seeking ultrasonography and other investigations in addition to supplementations or treatments given during pregnancy. Poor supervision and lack of in-service training resulted in midwives providing services not as expected.

CONCLUSION

- Almost all of the study midwives recognized the high risk pregnancy and indication of referral during pregnancy, labour, and postpartum period.
- Regarding antenatal care the majority of midwives conduct general examination and pregnant examination (fundal height, position of the fetus, presenting part, engagement, fetal heart sound auscultation, and lower limb edema) but ignored taking social, medical and obstetric history. Majority of them did not request investigations, measure the blood pressure or hear the fetal heart sounds which are very important for detection of any abnormality.
- The package of services provided by the midwives is lack family planning, health education, social mobilization, and registration of maternal and neonatal death.
- Mother's satisfaction with ANC midwifery services was high.
- The recent in-service training ignored the basic Knowledge and practice related to midwifery.

RECOMMENDATION

1. Federal Ministry of Health (FMOH) to consider equipping midwives with basic kits such as sphygmomanometer and ambo bag with training on how to be used.
2. FMOH to consider equipping midwives with sophisticated investigation tools and trained them on how to use.
3. FMOH to revise in-service training contents to include refreshing courses on standard management of pregnancy and labor with up to date technology.
4. State Ministry of Health to secure jobs for all midwives.
5. FMOH and State Ministry of Health to perform frequent follow-up evaluation of midwives' performance and to avail fund and logistics for the supervisory visits is mandatory.

REFERENCES

- Abd Elmoneim O, Al-Khalifa, Shamim B, Kuppawamy (2014). Evaluation of Midwifery Knowledge on Antenatal Care in Omdurman Maternity Hospital Sudan. American Research Institute for Policy Development. International Journal of Health Sciences. June.
- Adegoke AA, Hofman JJ, Kongnyuy EJ, van den Broek N (2011). Monitoring and evaluation of skilled birth attendance: a proposed new framework. *Midwifery*; 27 (3):350–9. [PubMed]
- Carr C, Fauveau V, Fogstad H, Garden B, Johnson P, Laski L. et al (2011). Delivering Saving..
- Choulagai et al. (2013). Barriers to using skilled birth attendants' services in mid- and far-western Nepal: a cross-sectional study. *BMC International Health and Human Rights* 13:49.
- Dowswell T, Carroli G, Duley L, Gates S, Gülmezoglu AM, Khan-Neelofur D, Piaggio GGP (2010). Alternative versus standard packages of antenatal care for low-risk pregnancy. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*, Issue 10. Art. No: CD000934. DOI:
- FMOH (2010). Sudan Household Health Survey.
- FMOH (2014). Multiple Indicators Cluster Survey
- Goals MD, Secretary-general UN (1995). National, regional, and worldwide estimates of stillbirth rates in 2009 with trends since 2010. p 3–6.
- Graham W, Bell J, Bullough C, De Brouwere V, van Lerberghe W, Antwerp (2001). ITG Press: Can skilled attendance at delivery reduce maternal mortality in developing countries? Safe motherhood strategies: a review of the evidence. p. 97–129.
- Hatem M, Sandall J, Devane D, Soltani H, Gates S (2008). Midwife-led versus other models of care for childbearing women. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*. Issue 4. Art. No.: CD004667.
- International Confederation of Midwives (2011). ICM International Definition of a Midwife.. Available from: <http://www.internationalmidwives.org/who-we-are/policy-and-practice/icm-international-definition-of-the-midwife>. (Accessed September 2016)
- International Confederation of Midwives (2013). Essential competencies for basic midwifery practice 2010: revised. (Accessed September 2016)
- International Labor Office (2012). International Standard Classification of Occupations ISCO-08: Volume 1: Structure, group definitions and correspondence tables. International Labor Office, Geneva;
- Koblinsky M, Matthews Z, Hussein J, Mavalankar D, Mridha MK, Anwar I, et al. (2006). Going to scale with professional skilled care. *Lancet*; 368 (9544):1377–86. [PubMed]
- Lassi ZS, Haider BA, Bhutta ZA (2010). Community-based intervention packages for reducing maternal and neonatal morbidity and mortality and improving neonatal outcomes. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*. Issue 11. Art. No: CD007754. DOI: 10.1002/14651858.CD007754.pub2.
- Lawn JE, Blencowe H, Pattinson R, et al. (2011). Stillbirths: Where? When? Why? How to make the data count? The Lancet's Stillbirths Series steering committee. *Apr*. DOI:10.1016/S0140-6736(10)62187-3.
- Lincetto O, Mothebesoane-Anoh S, Gomez P, Munjanja S (2006). Antenatal care: Opportunities for Africa's newborns: Practical data, policy and programmatic support for newborn care in Africa.:80-90.
- Minimum package of antenatal care services defined. Available from: URL (http://www.cpc.unc.edu/measure/prh/rh_indicators/specific/sm/minimum-package-of-antenatal-care-services-defined) (Accessed March 2017)
- Report S (2011). Stillbirths. *Summ Lancet [Internet]*;2(2):43–52. Available from: <http://www.springerlink.com/index/10.1007/BF02221151> (Accessed August 2016)
- Robinson S, Golden J, Bradley S (1983). A study of the role and responsibilities of the midwife. Chelsea College, University of London.
- Scott S, Ronsmans C (2009). The relationship between birth with a health professional and maternal mortality in observational studies: a review of the literature. *Trop Med Int Health*. 14(12):1523–33. [PubMed]
- Stanton C, Blanc AK, Croft T, Choi Y (2007). Skilled care at birth in the developing world: progress to date and strategies for expanding coverage. *Journal of biosocial science*. 39(01):109-20
- Suleiman Abd Gabbar Abdullah Bakheit (2010). Evaluation of midwifery services in North Kurdufan State.
- United Nations (2014). Assessing progress in Africa toward the Millennium Development Goals. United Nations Economic Commission for Africa.
- WHO, UNICEF, UNFPA and the World Bank (2015). Trends in maternal mortality: 1990–2015. Geneva: World Health Organization,.
- WHO, World Bank, UNICEF, UNFPA (2010). Packages of interventions for family planning, safe abortion care, maternal, newborn and child health WHO/FCH/10.06. Reproductive Health,.
- WHO. Geneva (2004). World Health Organization (WHO). Department of Reproductive Health and Research (RHR). Making pregnancy safer the critical role of the skilled attendant: a joint statement by WHO, ICM and FIGO.
- World Health Organization WHO Midwifery (2011). Available from <http://www.who.int/topics/midwifery/en> (Accessed September 2016)